

OF MONKS AND MOVABLE BEASTS: ANIMALS AS FELLOW TRAVELERS IN THE
NAVIGATIO SANCTI BRENDANI ABBATIS

Aylin Malcolm*

Abstract: This article examines the intersecting mobilities of humans and aquatic animals in the *Navigatio sancti Brendani abbatis*, an early account of the legendary maritime voyage of St. Brendan. Drawing on the “mobilities” framework that has emerged from the social sciences, I consider cases in which the physical movements of nonhuman animals mark changes in their relationships with humans. I argue that the *Navigatio* recognizes the potential for reciprocal influence between species while acknowledging the limits of human knowledge and experience. I describe the participants in these interspecies relationships as “travel companions,” a term inspired by Donna Haraway’s “companion species,” which I employ to convey the complexity and impermanence of their interactions. The *Navigatio* thus demonstrates the need for further work at the intersection of medieval animal studies and mobility studies.

Keywords: aquatic animals, companion species, marine ecosystems, marine mammals, mobility studies, St. Brendan, travel narrative

For the monks led by Brendan of Clonfert in the *Navigatio sancti Brendani abbatis* (Voyage of Saint Brendan the Abbot, henceforth *Navigatio*), a particular animal on the move seems to spell disaster. On Easter Eve, in the first year of their journey across the Atlantic Ocean, Brendan’s monks debark from their ship onto a strangely barren island, devoid of sand or grass. The monks rise early in the morning for Mass, then start to prepare a meal. Yet when they attempt to build a fire, the “island” begins to move, and the monks race back to the ship where Brendan has remained overnight, leaving their cooking pot behind (10.1–16).¹ Brendan hauls his crew onboard and reveals what he has learned from a recent vision:

Insula non est, ubi fuimus, sed piscis, prior omnium natancium in oceano. Querit semper ut suam caudam simul iungat capiti, et non potest pre longitudine. Qui habet nomen Jasconius.

[It is not an island where we were, but a fish, the first of all that swim in the ocean. He is always trying to connect his tail to his head and cannot due to his length. His name is Jasconius.] (10.24–26)

Although the *Navigatio* identifies Jasconius only as a *piscis* (fish), *bestia* (beast), and *belua* (monster), his initial actions resemble those of the aspidochelone, a legendary aquatic animal that entices sailors to land on its body, then dives into the sea. Medieval European texts often conflate this creature with whales, an interpretation consonant with Jasconius’s enormous size.² Yet Jasconius neither deliberately lures the monks onto his back nor dives after they inadvertently burn him; in fact, he swims for at least two miles with the fire blazing on his back (10.18–19). Moreover, when the monks sail on to an island populated by fallen angels who appear to them as birds, they learn that they are to spend the next six Easter Sundays on Jasconius’s back (11.35–37). Whale and humans then continue to meet year after year, their paths across the north Atlantic intersecting on this central feast of the liturgical calendar.

* Department of English, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, malcolma@sas.upenn.edu. I am very grateful to Przemyslaw T. Marciniak for editing this cluster and to the anonymous reviewers for their excellent suggestions.

¹ Quotations from the *Navigatio* follow Carl Selmer, ed., *Navigatio Sancti Brendani Abbatis from Early Latin Manuscripts* (South Bend, IN: University of Notre Dame Press, 1959). All translations throughout this article are my own.

² Bestiaries typically include two consecutive entries for the *aspidochelone* or *cetus* (sea monster) and the *balena* (whale), but the content of these entries could vary and overlap. See Willene B. Clark, *A Medieval Book of Beasts: The Second-Family Bestiary: Commentary, Art, Text and Translation* (Woodbridge: Boydell, 2006), 205–6; Dora Faraci, “*Navigatio Sancti Brendani* and Its Relationship with *Physiologus*,” *Romanobarbarica* 11 (1991): 149–73; Wilma George and William Brunsdon Yapp, *The Naming of the Beasts: Natural History in the Medieval Bestiary* (London: Duckworth, 1991), 95–96; Florence McCulloch, *Medieval Latin and French Bestiaries* (Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 2017), 91–92; Sebastian I. Sobocki, *The Sea and Middle English Literature* (Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 2008), 127–28; Vicki Ellen Szabo, *Monstrous Fishes and the Mead-Dark Sea: Whaling in the Medieval North Atlantic* (Leiden: Brill, 2008), 47–50.

As the temporary partnership between Jasconius and the monks illustrates, interspecies meetings in the *Navigatio* are often marked by physical and conceptual motion; thus as Jasconius alternates between movement and stasis, he also shifts in the monks' eyes from island to threat, and then to ally. This essay therefore approaches the *Navigatio* as a case study in how theories of mobility might be brought to bear on medieval animal studies and vice versa.³ I consider instances in which the physical movements of nonhuman creatures correspond to changes in the relationships between humans and other animals. Although the *Navigatio* generally upholds the supremacy of humans over nonhuman nature, a conventional view at the time of its composition, such hierarchies often prove unstable at sea, with humans relying on nonhuman knowledge and animals participating in religious celebrations.⁴ Taking inspiration from Donna Haraway's notion of "companion species" that continually "become with" one another via their relations—relations that are often complex and "troubled" rather than straightforwardly positive or negative—I refer to the participants in these encounters as "travel companions."⁵ This unusual hagiography therefore reveals the value of including nonhuman animals in research on mobility, within and beyond medieval studies.

Emerging during the 1990s, the cluster of critical approaches known as "mobility studies" or the "new mobilities paradigm" emphasizes movements and flows as integral components of human societies, past and present. Crucially, it advocates understand mobility not only as a thematic focus, but also as an interpretative mode that challenges "sedentarist" assumptions; rather than treating one's objects of study as stable and discrete by default, mobility theorists attend to their mutability and position within larger networks.⁶ Thus far, mobility studies has been most influential in social sciences such as cultural geography and sociology, but a recent issue of *postmedieval* on "Medieval Mobilities" speaks to the potential that it holds for premodernists, with articles on topics as diverse as language networks, textual transmission, pilgrimage, and plague. As the editors of this issue observe, the emphasis in mobility studies on transcultural networks complements recent efforts to develop global perspectives of the Middle Ages.⁷ Furthermore, while mobilities research often remains grounded in this paradigm's original focus on the movements of "people, ideas, objects, and information," some scholars have also addressed the mobilities of nonhuman life.⁸ For example, in her analysis of the flows of natural materials in Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales*, Sarah Breckenridge Wright notes that "ecocritical inquiry is an important part of any comprehensive consideration of mobility," while Kathleen Coyne Kelly's study of the spread of the Black

³ Previous scholarship on nonhuman species in the Brendan legends has often focused on the twelfth-century Anglo-Norman version rather than the *Navigatio*, the earliest manuscripts of which date from the tenth century. See, for example, Glyn S. Burgess, "The Use of Animals in Benedeit's Version of the Brendan Legend," in *The Brendan Legend: Texts and Versions*, ed. Clara Strijbosch and Glyn S. Burgess (Leiden: Brill, 2005), 11–34; Françoise H. M. Le Saux, "La Faune Marine Dans Le Voyage de Saint Brendan Anglo-Normand," *Reinardus* 21 (2008–09): 115–23; Liam Lewis, "Noise on the Ocean Before 'Pollution': The Voyage of Saint Brendan," forthcoming in *ISLE*.

⁴ In medieval philosophy, humans were typically distinguished from other animals as the sole species possessing rationality and an immortal soul. On this presumption of human dominance and the violence through which it was maintained, see Karl Steel, *How to Make a Human: Animals and Violence in the Middle Ages* (Columbus, OH: The Ohio State University Press, 2011), 14–23.

⁵ Donna Haraway, *When Species Meet* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2008), 16–19.

⁶ Mimi Sheller and John Urry, "The New Mobilities Paradigm," *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 38 (2006): 208–12. Recent monographs in this field include Tim Cresswell's *On the Move: Mobility in the Modern Western World* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2006), John Urry's *Mobilities* (Cambridge: Polity, 2007), Peter Merriman's *Mobility, Space and Culture* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2012), and Mimi Sheller's *Mobility Justice: The Politics of Movement in an Age of Extremes* (New York: Verso, 2018). For a discussion of mobility studies across various disciplines, see Peter Merriman et al., "Mobility: Geographies, Histories, Sociologies," *Transfers* 3 (2013): 147–65.

⁷ Martin B. Shichtman, Laurie A. Finke, and Kathleen Coyne Kelly, "'The World Is My Home When I'm Mobile': Medieval Mobilities," *postmedieval* 4 (2013): 126, 129. Scholarship on the Global Middle Ages is extensive and rapidly expanding, but as representative examples, see Geraldine Heng, *The Invention of Race in the European Middle Ages* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 257–86; Sierra Lomuto, "The Mongol Princess of Tars: Global Relations and Racial Formation in *The King of Tars* (c. 1330)," *Exemplaria* 31 (2019): 171–92; and the special issue edited by Geraldine Heng and Lynn Ramey on "The Global Middle Ages," *Literature Compass* 11 (2014).

⁸ Urry, *Mobilities*, 17.

Death incorporates discussion of genomic mapping.⁹ The mobilities paradigm therefore offers opportunities for linking the global turn in medieval studies to animal studies and the environmental humanities.

More specifically, the symbolic functions of marine ecosystems make them particularly useful for drawing these theoretical strands together. In medieval texts as in modern ones, the sea often represents the limits of human comprehension, the interconnectivity of the globe, and a state of placelessness among human travelers as well as its nonhuman inhabitants.¹⁰ Many texts written before the *Navigatio* discuss the mobilities of aquatic animals, from Ambrose's (c. 339–397) interpretation of fish migrations as a sign of divine providence to Isidore of Seville's (c. 560–636) description of the remora, a small fish that allegedly immobilized ships by attaching itself to them.¹¹ Marine animals also exhibited taxonomic mobility, troubling categories that could be more consistently applied to terrestrial creatures. Some, such as eels, were said to breed outside their species,¹² while others put pressure on the category of “animal” itself; thus several writers compared the sessile, ostensibly insensate bodies of shellfish to plants or stones.¹³

Similarly, medieval texts often depict the relationships between humans and aquatic species as precarious and changeable. In an essay on the later Anglo-Norman version of the Brendan narrative, Françoise Le Saux therefore cautions against allegorical readings that obscure the “inherent ambiguity” of sea monsters like Jasconius, with their capacity for violence as well as obedience to divine directives.¹⁴ Yet we might also approach aquatic animals in the *Navigatio* as inherently *mobile*—not only as eluding stable categorization, but also as existing within an ecosystem in which mobility is normative. Indeed, although Jasconius is immobile in his second appearance, traces of his former liveliness remain, such as the pot that the monks find on his back (15.33–34). By reminding readers of the true nature of this “island,” the text depicts stasis as an exceptional situation instigated by special providence.

The *Navigatio* also portrays humans as both affecting and affected by the mobile environment in which they find themselves: thus the monks' presence alters the whale's migratory habits, but Brendan's crew is also drawn into a cycle of movement and stasis. Following Liam Lewis, who argues that the Anglo-Norman text presents a “cross-species sonic relationality” extending beyond unidirectional notions of “noise pollution,” I therefore propose a similar understanding of movement in the *Navigatio*.¹⁵ Humans do not simply travel *through* the marine setting of this text, but travel *with* companion creatures in networks of mutual influence, and physical movement is often the cause or the outcome of shifts in their relationships. To be sure, traveling is only temporary. Here it is not the case, as in Haraway's “becoming with,” that relations precede or constitute the things being related.¹⁶ Yet “traveling with” does convey the irreducible complexity of these impermanent connections.

Another such encounter occurs on the feast of Saint Peter, after the monks have spent several Easters with Jasconius. Upon noticing a large number of animals resting on the seafloor, the monks ask their abbot to avoid disturbing these creatures by celebrating the feast in silence (21.1–10). Brendan

⁹ Sarah Breckenridge Wright, *Mobility and Identity in Chaucer's Canterbury Tales* (Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 2020), 14; Kathleen Coyne Kelly, “Flea and ANT: Mapping the Mobility of the Plague, 1330s–1350s,” *postmedieval* 4 (2013): 219–32.

¹⁰ On these typical views of the ocean, see Stacy Alaimo, “States of Suspension: Trans-Corporeality at Sea,” *ISLE* 19 (2012): 477, 489–90; Steven Mentz, “Toward a Blue Cultural Studies: The Sea, Maritime Culture, and Early Modern English Literature,” *Literature Compass* 6 (2009): 997–99.

¹¹ Ambrose, *Hexaameron*, PL 14 [1882]: 234a; Isidore of Seville, *Isidorum Hispalensis, Étymologies livre XII*, ed. Jacques André (Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1986), 6.34.

¹² Ambrose claimed that female *murænae* (eels or lampreys) mated with male vipers; *Hexaameron*, PL 14 [1882]: 227a–28c. See also Clark, *Book of Beasts*, 195–97.

¹³ For a summary of perspectives on oysters from Pliny the Elder to Philippe de Thaon and Ranulf Higden, see Karl Steel, *How Not to Make a Human: Pets, Feral Children, Worms, Sky Burial, Oysters* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2019), 135–64. Bestiaries often followed Isidore in attributing a degree of physical motion to shellfish, which were said to swell and shrink according to the lunar phase, but these texts did not make extravagant claims regarding their intentionality. See Clark, *Book of Beasts*, 213; Isidore, *Etymologiae*, 12.6.43.

¹⁴ Le Saux, “Faune Marine,” 123.

¹⁵ Lewis, “Noise on the Ocean.”

¹⁶ Haraway, *When Species Meet*, 17.

merely admonishes them for their lack of faith, asking: “Nonne Deus omnium bestiarum est Dominus noster Jhesus Christus, qui potest humiliare omnia animancia?” (Is not our lord Jesus Christ, who can humble all living things, the god of all beasts?; 21.15–17) His loud singing then wakes the creatures, which join in the celebrations by swimming around the boat. When Brendan finishes, the animals disperse so quickly that they soon disappear from view, despite the clear seawater (21.18–27).

The *Navigatio* does not elaborate on the precise nature of these beasts, although medieval readers might have associated them with dolphins, often described as swift animals with a penchant for human voices.¹⁷ Like Jasconius, they primarily serve to demonstrate God’s total authority over nature. At this point, it is worth noting that the desire to emphasize the unity of “all living things” often led medieval writers to anthropomorphize other species, granting them characteristics typically limited to humans—and this anthropomorphism could promote empathy and understanding across species lines.¹⁸ Thus the *Navigatio* seems to draw a parallel between human society and this group of aquatic animals, which it initially likens to a city on the seafloor (21.7), while the monks do appear to briefly consider the experiences of other species. Haylie Swenson accordingly reads this interaction as one of “shared aesthetic pleasure,” while Liam Lewis notes that it alerts the monks to the impacts of their actions on oceanic ecosystems, even though their motivations remain largely selfish.¹⁹

Nevertheless, the *Navigatio* avoids attributing any implausibly human behaviors to these creatures, which express themselves via swimming rather than song, and their physical movements reinforce the impression that the human/nonhuman boundary is not entirely permeable. The text indicates that “non appropinquabant nauicule, sed longe lateque natabant” (they did not draw near the boat, but swam far and wide; 21.22–23); that is, these creatures maintain a respectful distance from the frightened monks, while also remaining beyond the monks’ grasp in a figurative sense. As travel companions, humans and nonhumans each inspire piety in the other, and perhaps even concern for each other’s well-being, but the *Navigatio* preserves a sense of the alterity of nonhuman animals without reducing them to a purely symbolic function. In the end, these creatures disappear across a sea that the monks take days to navigate (21.24–27), a detail that highlights humans’ limited capacities in aquatic environments as well as their limited knowledge of the experiences of other species.

I have focused thus far on animals that interact with the traveling monks, but my use of “travel companions” to describe mobile and reciprocally influential relations can be extended to cases in which humans are not physically moving. The limits of human abilities again become apparent near the end of the monks’ journey, when they meet the ascetic whom Brendan calls “Paulum heremitam spiritalem” (Paul the spiritual hermit; 26.9) on a small island. In response to Brendan’s questions about his life in isolation, Paul explains that he relied on a remarkably long-lived otter, which brought him a fish every three days for thirty years.²⁰ This miraculous otter adopts a blend of lutrine and human mannerisms, first appearing to Paul with “piscem unum in ore suo, et fasciculum de sarmentis...inter suos anteriores pedes, ambulans super duobus posterioribus” (a fish in its mouth, and a bundle of twigs...between its front paws, walking on its two hind legs; 26.71–73).²¹ As Haraway observes, the term “companion” is related to the

¹⁷ Medieval descriptions of dolphins often draw on Pliny’s *Naturalis historia*, which describes them as the fastest creatures in the ocean and indicates their fondness for humans and music. See Clark, *Book of Beasts*, 207; Isidore, *Étymologies livre XII*, 6.11; Pliny the Elder, *Natural History, Volume III: Books 8–11*, ed. and trans. H. Rackham (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1940), 9.7–8. Burgess argues that the equivalent episode in the Anglo-Norman text depicts humpback whales; “Use of Animals,” 33.

¹⁸ Susan Crane explores this phenomenon in the second-family bestiaries; see *Animal Encounters: Contacts and Concepts in Medieval Britain* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2012), 69–100.

¹⁹ Haylie Swenson, “On the Backs of Whales,” in *Sea Monsters: Things from the Sea, Volume 2*, eds. Thea Thomani and Asa S. Mittman (Santa Barbara: punctum books, 2017), 33; Lewis, “Noise on the Ocean.”

²⁰ On the hagiographic tradition of nonhuman animals ministering to saints, see Dominic Alexander, *Saints and Animals in the Middle Ages* (Woodbridge: Boydell, 2008), 20–37.

²¹ In the Anglo-Norman version, the otter carries dried seaweed in a small bag rather than firewood; see Benedeit, *The Anglo-Norman Voyage of St. Brendan*, eds. Ian Short and Brian Merrilees (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1979), ll. 1571–72. Since sea otters use kelp to anchor themselves while they sleep, this satchel also suggests a convergence between human and nonhuman expertise.

Latin *cum panis* (with bread), reflecting the tradition of sharing food while building alliances, interspecies and otherwise.²² In this marine setting, the otter instead arrives *cum piscibus* (with fish), welcoming Paul by offering him its own customary meal, while also bringing firewood to accommodate the human practice of cooking one's food.

Perhaps the most striking element of this description, however, is the otter's unusual posture. Sea otters are capable of living exclusively in the ocean and would be unlikely to walk on their hind legs in nature, although they are occasionally trained to do so in captivity.²³ This otter's bipedal motion therefore reinforces the sense that it is attempting to meet Paul midway. By walking upright with a bundle in its hands, it mimics a human bringing a gift, but Paul also depends on this otter because of its nonhuman traits, particularly its superior fishing skills and its ability to move from the sea onto the shore. Indeed, the otter quickly disappears after delivering these materials to Paul, returning to an aquatic world inaccessible to humans (26.74). Even though these individuals are not literally traveling together, with Paul remaining on his island, their relationship can therefore be understood as a travel companionship due to its bidirectional nature, the autonomy of its participants, and the role of movement in bridging the gap between species.

Like Jasconius and the St. Peter's Day celebrants, Paul's otter companion is a legible sign of God's influence in the world, but this passage also establishes that relations between humans and other animals may be reciprocal and transformative. In the *Navigatio*, the physical movements of animals such as these are often responses to human actions and desires; thus Jasconius accommodates the monks by limiting his mobility, the rapid swimming of the animals in the clear sea complements Brendan's religious fervor, and the otter travels between ocean and land while providing for a human in need. These movements may be comprehensible to humans, such as the whale's reflexive reaction to fire, or they may attest to experiences that lie beyond human understanding, but they consistently reveal nonhuman animals to be more than unthinking instruments of the monks' spiritual development. These creatures interact with humans as travel companions, developing relations that are significant despite their transience.

Indeed, such companionships remain significant for Brendan and his crew until the conclusion of their journey. In Jasconius's seventh and final appearance, he surprises the monks by beginning to move while they are on his back. Yet in contrast to their initial encounter, Brendan recognizes the whale's actions as benevolent, informing his crew that "adiutorium imminet itineris" (help for the journey is here; 27.18–19). Jasconius then ferries them to the island of the birds, from which they set off for the Promised Land of the Saints. By linking the fulfillment of the monks' spiritual voyage to the whale's migratory instincts, the text again affirms the value of nonhuman experiences and interspecies collaborations. The *Navigatio* thus speaks to the importance of studying the mobilities of aquatic animals and other nonhuman creatures in all periods. Though we live in a time of unprecedented global mobility, premodern texts reveal that we have never traveled alone.

²² Haraway, *When Species Meet*, 17.

²³ In 2020, a sea otter at an aquarium in central Japan learned to walk on her hind legs. See the Twitter post by the Toba Aquarium account, September 10, 2020, 5:10 PM JST, https://twitter.com/TOBA_AQUARIUM/status/1303969152097333249.

Bibliography

Primary Sources and Texts

- Ambrose. *Hexameron*. Edited by Jacques Paul Migne. *Patrologia Latina* 14: 219–72. Paris: Garnier, 1882.
- Benedeit. *The Anglo-Norman Voyage of St. Brendan*. Edited by Ian Short and Brian Merrilees. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1979.
- Clark, Willene B. *A Medieval Book of Beasts: The Second-Family Bestiary: Commentary, Art, Text and Translation*. Woodbridge: Boydell, 2006.
- Isidore of Seville. *Isidorum Hispalensis, Étymologies livre XII*. Edited by Jacques André. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1986.
- Pliny the Elder. *Natural History, Volume III: Books 8–11*. Edited and translated by H. Rackham. Loeb Classical Library 353. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1940.
- Selmer, Carl, ed. *Navigatio Sancti Brendani Abbatis from Early Latin Manuscripts*. South Bend, IN: University of Notre Dame Press, 1959.

Secondary Sources

- Alaimo, Stacy. “States of Suspension: Trans-corporeality at Sea.” *ISLE* 19 (2012): 476–93.
- Alexander, Dominic. *Saints and Animals in the Middle Ages*. Woodbridge: Boydell, 2008.
- Burgess, Glyn S. “The Use of Animals in Benedeit’s Version of the Brendan Legend.” In *The Brendan Legend: Texts and Versions*, edited by Clara Strijbosch and Glyn S. Burgess, 11–34. Leiden: Brill, 2005.
- Crane, Susan. *Animal Encounters: Contacts and Concepts in Medieval Britain*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2012.
- Cresswell, Tim. *On the Move: Mobility in the Modern Western World*. Abingdon: Routledge, 2006.
- Faraci, Dora. “*Navigatio Sancti Brendani* and Its Relationship with *Physiologus*.” *Romanobarbarica* 11 (1991): 149–73.
- George, Wilma, and William Brunsdon Yapp. *The Naming of the Beasts: Natural History in the Medieval Bestiary*. London: Duckworth, 1991.
- Haraway, Donna. *When Species Meet*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2008.
- Heng, Geraldine. *The Invention of Race in the European Middle Ages*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- Heng, Geraldine, and Lynn Ramey, eds. “The Global Middle Ages.” Special issue, *Literature Compass* 11 (2014).
- Kelly, Kathleen Coyne. “Flea and ANT: Mapping the Mobility of the Plague, 1330s–1350s.” *postmedieval* 4 (2013): 219–32.
- Le Saux, Françoise H. M. “La faune marine dans le *Voyage de Saint Brendan* anglo-normand.” *Reinardus* 21 (2008–09): 115–23.
- Lewis, Liam. “Noise on the Ocean Before ‘Pollution’: The Voyage of Saint Brendan.” Forthcoming in *ISLE*.
- Lomuto, Sierra. “The Mongol Princess of Tars: Global Relations and Racial Formation in *The King of Tars* (c. 1330).” *Exemplaria* 31 (2019): 171–92.
- McCulloch, Florence. *Medieval Latin and French Bestiaries*. Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 2017.
- Mentz, Steven. “Toward a Blue Cultural Studies: The Sea, Maritime Culture, and Early Modern English Literature.” *Literature Compass* 6 (2009): 997–1013.
- Merriman, Peter. *Mobility, Space, and Culture*. Abingdon: Routledge, 2012.
- Merriman, Peter, Rhys Jones, Tim Cresswell, Colin Divall, Gijs Mom, Mimi Sheller, and John Urry. “Mobility: Geographies, Histories, Sociologies.” *Transfers* 3 (2013): 147–65.

- Sheller, Mimi. *Mobility Justice: The Politics of Movement in an Age of Extremes*. New York: Verso, 2018.
- Sheller, Mimi, and John Urry. "The New Mobilities Paradigm." *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 38 (2006): 207–26.
- Shichtman, Martin B., Laurie A. Finke, and Kathleen Coyne Kelly. "'The World Is My Home When I'm Mobile': Medieval Mobilities." *postmedieval* 4 (2013): 125–35.
- Sobecki, Sebastian I. *The Sea and Middle English Literature*. Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 2008.
- Steel, Karl. *How Not to Make a Human: Pets, Feral Children, Worms, Sky Burial, Oysters*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2019.
- . *How to Make a Human: Animals and Violence in the Middle Ages*. Columbus, OH: The Ohio State University Press, 2011.
- Swenson, Haylie. "On the Backs of Whales." In *Sea Monsters: Things from the Sea, Volume 2*, edited by Thea Thomani and Asa S. Mittman, 18–33. *tiny collections* 3. Santa Barbara: punctum books, 2017.
- Szabo, Vicki Ellen. *Monstrous Fishes and the Mead-Dark Sea: Whaling in the Medieval North Atlantic*. *The Northern World* 35. Leiden: Brill, 2008.
- Toba Aquarium (鳥羽水族館). Twitter post. September 10, 2020, 5:10 PM JST. https://twitter.com/TOBA_AQUARIUM/status/1303969152097333249.
- Urry, John. *Mobilities*. Cambridge: Polity, 2007.
- Wright, Sarah Breckenridge. *Mobility and Identity in Chaucer's Canterbury Tales*. *Chaucer Studies* 46. Cambridge: D.S. Brewer, 2020.